

SYNCHRONIZING THE BIOLOGICAL CLOCK: A CHRONOBIOLOGICAL REVIEW
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ABSTRACT

Chronobiology, though a modern scientific concept, has deep roots in Ayurveda. Ancient Ayurvedic texts emphasized living in harmony with natural cycles—sun, moon, and seasonal rhythms—through practices like *Dinacharya* (daily routine) and *Ritucharya* (seasonal regimen). The principle of *Lok Purusha Samanya Siddhanta* highlights that human health reflects universal rhythms. Modern research on circadian biology, including the role of the hypothalamic suprachiasmatic nucleus and findings on chrono-nutrition, neuroendocrine regulation, and seasonal variation in metabolism, aligns closely with these classical concepts. The Ayurvedic idea of *Dosha Kala* parallels circadian patterns in hormone release, metabolism, and cognition, while *Ritucharya* resonates with recent studies on gut microbiome shifts and metabolic changes across seasons. These correlations reaffirm that Ayurvedic lifestyle practices not only prevent disease and promote well-being but also maintain psychophysiological balance. Integrating this ancient wisdom with modern chronobiology encourages multidisciplinary approaches to personalized healthcare.

KEYWORDS: *Chronobiology, Dinacharya, Circadian rhythm, ritucharya.*

INTRODUCTION

The biochemical, physiological, and behavioural activities of all living organisms on Earth, including fungi, cyanobacteria, plants, and animals, are governed by circadian rhythms—approximately 24-hour cycles. The term *circadian* is derived from the Latin words *circa* (“around”) and *diem/dies* (“day”), meaning “approximately one day.” Chronobiology, the scientific discipline devoted to the study of temporal biological rhythms, encompasses circadian (daily), circatidal, circaseptan (weekly), circannual (seasonal), and annual cycles.

Ayurveda, one of the world’s oldest systems of medicine, provides a unique perspective on chronobiology through the concept of the three *doshas*—Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. Like how *Soma*, *Surya*, and *Anila* preserve the integrity of the terrestrial universe, the *doshas* maintain the integrity of the human body by generating, absorbing, and dispersing vitality, as described by Sushruta. All metabolic processes are believed to be regulated by the circadian cycle of these *doshas*, and disturbances in their rhythm are the root cause of various disease states.

In addition to circadian regulation, *doshas* are also subject to circannual rhythms, which align with seasonal variations. The states of *Sanchaya* (accumulation), *Prokop* (aggravation), and *Shamana* (pacification) describe the seasonal dynamics of *doshas*, thereby influencing biochemical, physiological, and behavioural functions. Furthermore, the predominance of different *doshas* shifts with age: *Kapha* dominates in childhood (*Balyavastha*), *Pitta* in middle age (*Madhya-Avastha*), and *Vata* in old age (*Vaidhyathanan*). *Vagbhata* emphasized that the *doshas* become ascendant according to *Vaya* (age), *kaal* (time/period), and stages of the digestive process.

Ayurveda also recognizes the impact of seasonal changes on *dosha* rhythms, manifesting as cyclical states of *Sanchaya*, *Prakopa*, and *Prashama*. These fluctuations influence an individual’s *bala* (strength), which varies between *Adana Kala* (northern solstice, hot and dry) and *Visarga Kala* (southern solstice, cold and moist). To maintain equilibrium, Ayurveda prescribes lifestyle and dietary regimens—*Dinacharya* (daily routines) and *Ritucharya* (seasonal routines)—as adaptive strategies to align human physiology with environmental cycles.

Thus, the Ayurvedic framework of chronobiology underscores the intimate connection between temporal biological rhythms and health. Failure to adhere to these natural cycles may result in *dosha* vitiation, predisposing individuals to disease. This concept parallels modern chronobiological research, which links altered circadian rhythms to various pathological states.

Literature Review

Ritucharya

According to *Ayurveda*, the year is divided into two distinct sections based on the movement of the sun. These are known as *Uttarayana* (the northern solstice) and *Dakshinayana* (the southern solstice). Each comprises three seasons, or *Ritus*. The term *Ritu* in Sanskrit means “to go,” signifying the orderly manifestation of nature in its various forms, or simply the seasons.^[1]

In *Uttarayana*, the seasons are *Shishira* (winter), *Vasanta* (spring), and *Grishma* (summer), while in *Dakshinayana* they are *Varsha* (monsoon), *Sharad* (autumn), and *Hemanta* (late autumn). Seasonal variations are most prominent in the Indian subcontinent, where *Ayurveda* was first practiced. Regarding the state of strength, weakness is experienced during *Varsha* and *Grishma*—marking the beginning of *Visarga Kala* and the end of *Adana Kala*. Maximum strength is observed during *Hemanta* and *Shishira*, which correspond to the end of *Visarga Kala* and the beginning of *Adana Kala*. A moderate strength state is maintained during *Sharad* and *Vasanta*, which represent the middle solstices.^[2]

Regimen of Different Seasons

1. Shishira (Winter)

Overall State

Shishira Ritu occurs from mid-January to mid-March. The weather remains cold with chilly winds. During this period, *Tikta* (bitter) is the dominant *Rasa*, while *Akasha* is the predominant *Mahabhuta*. *Agni* (catabolic activity) remains strong, *Kapha Dosha* begins to accumulate, and physical strength tends to decline.

Diet

Foods with a strong *Amla* (sour) taste are preferred. Fresh rice, corn, wheat, gram flour products, cereals, and pulses are recommended. Items such as ginger, garlic, *pippali* (*Piper longum*), *haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*), sugarcane products, and milk and milk-based preparations are beneficial. Foods with excessive *Katu* (pungent).

Tikta (bitter), or *Kashaya* (astringent) tastes should be avoided. Similarly, *Shita* (cold) and *Laghu* (light) foods are not recommended.

Lifestyle

Practices such as oil massage, powder massage, or paste application, followed by a lukewarm bath, are advised. Exposure to sunlight and warm clothing are beneficial.

Activities that aggravate *Vata*—such as late-night wakefulness, excessive walking, or exposure to cold winds—should be avoided.

2. Vasanta (Spring)

Overall State

Vasanta Ritu spans from mid-March to mid-May. This season is marked by the blooming of flowers and the sprouting of new leaves. The dominant *Mahabhutas* are *Vayu* and *Prithvi*, while the predominant *Rasa* is *Kashaya* (astringent). During this time, *Agni* becomes *Manda* (weakened), *Kapha Dosha* becomes vitiated, and physical strength remains moderate.

Diet

Easily digestible foods are recommended. Old barley, wheat, rice, and cereals should be consumed, along with pulses such as lentils and *mudga* (green gram). *Bitter* (*Tikta*), *pungent* (*Katu*), and *astringent* (*Kashaya*) foods are ideal. Honey is especially beneficial. Easily digestible meats, such as that of *Shasha* (rabbit), may also be included. Heavy-to-digest, *Sheeta* (cold), *Snigdha* (unctuous), *Guru* (heavy), *Amla* (sour), or *Madhura* (sweet) foods should be avoided, along with cold drinks, curd, and freshly harvested grains.

Lifestyle

Warm baths and regular exercise are beneficial. *Ayurvedic* practices such as *Udvartana* (massage with herbal powders like *Chandana* (*Santalum album*), *Kesara* (*Crocus sativus*), and *Agaru*), *Kavala* (gargling), *Dhooma* (medicated smoking), *Anjana* (collyrium), as well as purification measures like *Vamana* and *Nasya*, are recommended. Daytime sleeping should be strictly avoided.

In *Vasant Ritu* (spring), *Ayurveda* notes *kapha* aggravation causing lethargy and poor digestion, recommending light, pungent, bitter foods like barley, honey, and ginger. Modern findings support this—seasonal immune shifts and fatigue in spring are documented (Nelson et al., 2016, PNAS), while ginger and honey show proven anti-inflammatory and digestive benefits (Mashhadi et al., 2013, Int J Prev Med; Erejuwa et al., 2012, Molecules), validating *Ayurvedic* prescriptions.

3. Grishma (Summer)

Overall State

Grishma Ritu extends from mid-May to mid-July. The climate during this period is extremely harsh, characterized by hot winds, intense sunlight, and high temperatures. Vegetation dries up, riverbeds deplete, and the environment appears arid. *Katu* (pungent) is the dominant *Rasa*, while *Agni* and *Vayu* predominate among the *Mahabhutas*. During this season, the vitiated *Kapha Dosha* is calmed, but the individual's strength declines, and *Vata Dosha* begins to accumulate. *Agni* remains mild.

Diet

The diet should include rice, lentils, and other preparations possessing *Madhura* (sweet), *Snigdha* (unctuous), *Sheeta* (cold), and *Drava* (liquid) qualities. Ample fluids are recommended, such as cold water, buttermilk, fruit juices, meat soups, mango juice, and spiced curd. Before bedtime, milk with sugar-based sweets is considered beneficial. Foods with *Lavana* (salty), *Katu* (pungent), or *Amla* (sour) tastes, as well as *Ushna* (hot) preparations, should be avoided.

Lifestyle

Daytime sleep, wearing light clothing, applying sandalwood and other fragrant pastes, and staying in cool environments are advised. Exposure to the soothing rays of the moon and cool night breezes is beneficial. Activities such as excessive physical exertion, indulgence in sexual pleasure, and alcohol consumption should be avoided. During Grishma Ritu, the body's thermoregulatory mechanisms intensify, leading to increased sweating. This heightened perspiration can alter skin hydration and pH levels, potentially disrupting the skin's natural barrier. Modern studies indicate that excessive sweating during this period may result in elevated skin surface pH and reduced hydration, which can compromise skin health.

Ayurveda, recognizing the dominance of the Pitta dosha during this season, recommends the consumption of *Sheeta* (cooling) foods to counteract the internal heat and maintain balance. Incorporating cooling foods such as cucumbers, melons, dairy, and herbal drinks aligns with both modern understanding and Ayurvedic practices to support the body's natural cooling processes.

Therefore, integrating cooling foods into the diet during Grishma Ritu is essential for maintaining internal and external harmony, supporting both physiological and dermatological health

4. Varsha (Monsoon)**Overall State**

Varsha Ritu occurs approximately from mid-July to mid-September. The season is marked by cloudy skies, continuous rainfall without thunder, and abundant water in rivers, ponds, and lakes. *Agni*, *Prithvi*, and *Amla* (sour) dominate during this season. *Vata Dosha* becomes vitiated, *Pitta Dosha* accumulates, digestive *Agni* is weakened, and physical strength declines.

Diet

Sour (Amla), *salty (Lavana)*, and *unctuous (Sneha)* foods are recommended. Old rice, wheat, barley, and similar cereals should be consumed. Meat soups and *yusha* (vegetable soups) are beneficial. Warm or medicated water is advised for drinking. Alcohol, excessive liquid intake, over-diluted churned preparations, river water, and heavy indigestible foods should be avoided.

Lifestyle

After bathing in warm water, the body should be massaged with oil. Medicated *Basti* (enema) is considered ideal for eliminating vitiated *Doshas*. Prohibited practices include direct exposure to rain, daytime sleep, overexertion, sexual indulgence, windy environments, and staying near riverbanks. During the rainy season, *Agni* (digestive fire) is naturally lowered according to Ayurveda, predisposing individuals to digestive disturbances. Modern research shows that high humidity and seasonal changes can disrupt gut microbiota, impairing digestion. Ayurveda recommends warm, easily digestible foods and digestive spices to support *Agni*, which aligns with contemporary understanding of maintaining gut microbial balance. Thus, monsoon dietary practices in Ayurveda resonate with modern strategies for digestive health.

5. Sharad (Autumn)**Overall State**

Sharad Ritu spans from mid-September to mid-November. The environment is characterized by damp soil, clear skies with scattered white clouds, and bright sunshine. The predominant *Mahabhutas* are *Aap* and *Agni*, while the primary *Rasa* is *Lavana* (salty). During this period, *Agni* becomes strong, *Vata Dosha* is pacified, *Pitta Dosha* becomes vitiated, and physical strength remains moderate.

Diet

Light-to-digest (*Laghu*), cooling foods with *Madhura* (sweet) and *Tikta* (bitter) tastes are recommended, particularly those that pacify vitiated *Pitta*. Wheat, green gram, honey, sugar preparations, *patola (Trichosanthes dioica)*, and the meat of dry-land animals (*Jangala Mamsa*) are ideal. Spicy, excessively bitter, heavy, fatty, or astringent foods, as well as curd, oils, and aquatic meat, should be avoided.

Lifestyle

Eating should be done only in the presence of genuine appetite. Water should be purified by exposure to the sun during the day and the moon at night before drinking or bathing. Wearing garlands, applying *Chandana (Santalum album)* paste, and exposure to moonlight during the early night hours are beneficial. Therapies such as *Rakta-Mokshana* (bloodletting) and *Virechana* (purgation) are especially indicated. Excessive food intake, daytime sleep, and prolonged sun exposure should be avoided. In *Sharad Ritu*, the body's internal heat (*Pitta*) increases due to the transition from the cool monsoon to the dry autumn, leading to skin conditions like acne, rashes, and eczema. Modern studies indicate that seasonal changes, such as increased humidity and temperature fluctuations, can disrupt skin barrier function and exacerbate inflammatory skin disorders. Ayurveda recommends cooling and soothing treatments, such as *Kumkumadi* oil, to balance *Pitta* and support skin health during this season. This approach aligns with

contemporary dermatological practices that emphasize maintaining skin hydration and reducing inflammation.

6. Hemanta (Late Autumn)

Overall State

Hemanta Ritu is observed from mid-November to mid-January. Cold winds begin to blow, and the temperature drops considerably. The predominant *Rasa* is *Madhura* (sweet), while *Prithvi* and *Aap* are the major *Mahabhutas*. During this season, strength is at its peak, *Pitta Dosha* is pacified, and digestive *Agni* becomes highly active.

Diet

Foods rich in sweetness, sourness, and saltiness are preferred. Freshly harvested rice, wheat flour preparations, green gram, *masha* (black gram), and other cereals and pulses are recommended. Foods aggravating *Vata*—such as light (*Laghu*), cold, and dry preparations—should be avoided. Cold beverages are also contraindicated.

Lifestyle

Physical activity, oil massage of the body and head, warm baths, sun exposure (*Atapa Sevana*), application of *Agaru* paste, heavy clothing, and regulated sexual activity are advised. Warm environments are ideal. Avoid exposure to strong cold winds, excessive cold, and daytime sleeping.^[3-8]

During the Hemanta (early winter) and Shishira (late winter) seasons, physiological studies have shown increased sympathetic nervous system activity and peripheral vasoconstriction in response to cold exposure, which aligns with Ayurvedic principles emphasizing the body's need for warmth and internal stability during these colder months.

Dinacharya (Daily Regimen)

The regimen of *Dinacharya*, as explained by the classical Acharyas, is an authentic method of dietary regulation and engagement in mental and physical practices that benefit a person not only in the present life but also in future existence. *Acharya Arunadatta* emphasizes that *Dinacharya* sustains well-being across lifetimes.^[9] *Acharya Sushruta* underscores the importance of a healthy digestive system, balanced *Doshas*, and the harmony of mind and body in maintaining health.^[10]

To fully comprehend the importance of such a regimen, one must understand certain foundational *Ayurvedic* principles. These include the *Samanya-Visheshha Siddhanta* (the principle of similarity and

dissimilarity),^[11] the *Sarva Vyadhi Nidana* (the theory describing the fundamental causes of diseases)^[12] and the concept of *Kriya Kaal* (the temporal stages of *Dosha* imbalance and opportunities for correction).^[13]

According to *Samanya-Visheshha Siddhanta*, similar qualities in food or activities increase corresponding bodily factors, while opposing qualities reduce them. Thus, in daily practice, intentional consumption of foods and adoption of activities may be used to either enhance diminished *Dosha-Dhatu* elements or to reduce those that are in excess, thereby establishing harmony.

The principle of *Sarva Vyadhi Nidana* recognizes that health and disease depend upon the interaction of *Kala* (time), *Artha* (sensory perception), and *Karma* (actions). When these are inappropriately related—whether by deficiency (*Hina Yoga*), excess (*Ati Yoga*), or erroneous use (*Mithya Yoga*)—disease manifests. In contrast, their appropriate coordination (*Samyak Yoga*) leads to health. Hence, awareness of *Dinacharya* in this context means aligning one's daily mental, verbal, and physical activities with these three factors to maintain health.

The concept of *Kriya Kaal* highlights the stages of disease development, providing windows of opportunity for preventive or corrective intervention. If causative factors persist unaddressed, disharmony in *Doshas* and *Dhatu*s progresses toward disease. In this context, *Kriya* denotes corrective actions, while *Kaal* emphasizes the timely execution of these actions. Lifestyle errors such as inappropriate eating, drinking, or physical and mental activities contribute to ongoing disharmony, whereas adherence to proper regimens presents an opportunity to restore balance.

When implemented correctly, *Dinacharya* exerts profound influence on the body's structural and functional components, digestion, and metabolism. Proper daily practices help prevent and correct illnesses, enhance longevity, and delay the onset of disease. With adherence, the biological clock becomes regulated, tissues are rejuvenated, sense organs are strengthened, mental calm and balance are restored, and physical strength is increased. Collectively, these benefits result in healthy aging, vitality, and improved lifespan.^[14]

Thus, the framework of *Dinacharya*, grounded in classical *Ayurvedic* principles, provides not only preventive and promotive health strategies but also forms a cornerstone in lifestyle-based disease management. The following presents a detailed enumeration of *Dinacharya* according to various Acharyas.”

Charaka ^[15]	Sushruta ^[16]	Ashtanga Hridaya ^[17]
Anjana	Dantapavana	Brahme muhurte uttishthet
Dhumapana	Mukhaprakshalana	Shauchavidhi
Nasya	Netraprakshalana	Dantadhavana
Anutaila	Anjana	Anjana
Dantadhavana	Tambula Bhakshana	Nasya

Jivha Nirlekhana	Shirah Pratipurana	Gandusha
Tambulabhakshana	Keshprasadhana	Dhumapana
Taila Gandusha	Karnapurana	Tambulasevana
Shirahsneha Dharana	Tailabhyanga	Tailabhyanga
Karnapura	Sarvanga parisheka	Vyayama
Tailabhyanga	Snehavagahana	Dehamardana
Padabhyanga	Abhyanga	Udvardana
Udvardana	Vyayama	Snana
Snana	Deha mardana	Hita Mita Bhojana
Vastra Dharna	Udvardana, Udgharshana, Utsadana	Ratna, Siddhamantra Dharana
Gandhamalya Dharana	Snana Anulepana, Pushpa Dharana	Mahaushadhi Dharana
Ratna Dharana	Vastradharana	Aataptra Dharana
Hasta Pada Shuchita	Ratnadharana	Paadatrana Dharana
Kesha Shmashru Kartana	Mukhalepa	Kesha, Shmashru, Nakha Kartana
Padatrana Dhrana	Anjana	Padaprakshalana
Chhatra Dharana	Devata pujan	Shrotradimalasamhara
Danda Dharan	Ahara	Snana

Dinacharya and Its Scientific Correlates

1) Brahma-Muhurta-Utthana (Early Morning Awakening)

Waking 45 minutes before sunrise (*Brahma Muhurta*) is advocated in *Ayurveda*, provided the previous night's food is digested. Rising at this time ensures proper *dosha* balance and metabolic health.^[18] The term *Brahma* signifies knowledge; thus, this period is considered auspicious for learning and spiritual practices.^[19] Cortisol, the primary glucocorticoid with anti-stress and immunomodulatory functions, peaks within 30 minutes of waking, supporting the *Ayurvedic* claim of enhanced well-being during this period^[20,21] Modern research also confirms that Brahma Muhurta fosters mental, social, physical, and spiritual health.^[22]

2. Shauchavidhi (Defecation and Urination)

Early morning urges are governed by *Apana Vata*. Suppression may predispose to systemic disorders, including cardiac and ocular diseases.^[25,26]

3. Dantadhavana (Tooth Brushing)

Charaka advises daily brushing, while *Vagbhata* recommends brushing both in the morning and after meals.^[27,28] Traditionally, herbal twigs with bitter or astringent tastes, such as *Karanja*, *Asana*, *Nyagrodha*, and *Arjuna*, are used.^[29] Unlike modern toothpaste with synthetic additives, which may cause adverse effects^[30] these natural methods preserve oral health.

4. Jihva-Nirlekhana (Tongue Cleaning)

Ayurveda recommends scraping the tongue with a metal or herbal strip to alleviate *Kapha*, correct halitosis, and improve taste perception.^[31] Biomedical studies validate its role in reducing bacterial load and improving taste bud function.^[32]

5. Gandusha and Kavala (Oil Pulling)

Oil pulling strengthens teeth and gums, improves voice, prevents dryness, and ensures dental stability.^[33] Clinical studies demonstrate its effectiveness against

Streptococcus mutans, gingivitis, and plaque, comparable to chlorhexidine but without discoloration side effects.^[34,35] It also reduces oral microbial burden and increases salivary defence.^[36,37]

6. Anjana (Collyrium Application)

Regular use of Anjana alleviates ocular *dosha* imbalances and maintains clarity of vision.^[38] Two types are described: *Sauviranjana* for daily use and *Rasanjana* for *Kapha* disorders.^[39] Modern studies suggest benefits in nasolacrimal duct patency and vision improvement in ocular pathologies.^[40,41]

7. Nasya (Medicated Nasal Drops)

Daily administration of nasal oils enhances sensory functions, prevents premature hair greying, and treats disorders like migraine, facial paralysis, and rhinitis.^[42,43] Recent research links *Anutaila Nasya* with improved quality of life and resilience against COVID-19.^[44,45]

8. Abhyanga (Oil Massage)

Daily oil massage nourishes tissues, delays aging, improves sleep, skin health, and circulation, and calms *Vata*.^[46] Research shows *Abhyanga* enhances serotonin and melatonin levels, thereby restoring circadian rhythm.^[47] Studies confirm benefits in anti-aging^[48], scalp hair health^[49,50], and cardiac autonomic regulation.^[51,52]

9. Vyayama (Exercise)

Ayurveda prescribes moderate, seasonal exercise to improve stamina, metabolism, circulation, and disease resistance.^[53] Modern evidence shows benefits in cognition, hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular health.^[54-57] Over-exertion, however, is contraindicated, leading to *Vata* aggravation and systemic disorders.^[58]

10. Snana (Bathing)

Bathing improves digestion, vitality, skin health, and mental freshness.^[59] Caution is advised in conditions such as indigestion, diarrhoea, or after meals.

11. Bhojana (Food Practices)

Ayurveda emphasizes *Ahara Matra* (quantity), *Ashana Kala* (meal timing), *Anupana* (liquid adjuncts), *Viruddha Ahara* (incompatible foods), and *Ahara Vidhi Visheshayatana* (specific food rules).^[60-63] These dietary principles maintain *dosha-dhatu* balance.

12. Sadvrutta (Code of Conduct)

In addition to physical regimen, *Ayurveda* stresses ethical and mental conduct for psychosocial well-being. *Sadvrutta* promotes *Satva guna* (clarity of mind) and balances mental *doshas*.^[64-66] Neglect leads to disturbed relationships, aggression, and poor coping abilities.

DISCUSSION

Modern chronobiology reveals that both daily and seasonal rhythms profoundly shape human physiology. Gene expression, metabolism, and gut microbiota show distinct circadian and seasonal patterns influenced by

light, temperature, diet, and environmental cycles. These findings parallel the *Ayurvedic* principles of *Dincharya* and *Ritucharya*, which emphasize aligning lifestyle with natural temporal rhythms.

Daily routines such as waking, eating, and sleeping in sync with the circadian clock help optimize metabolic and hormonal balance, while seasonal adjustments in diet, behaviour, and sleep support adaptation to changing environmental demands. The concept of *Agni* (digestive fire) can be understood in this context as the body's temporally regulated metabolic capacity, sensitive to both daily and seasonal shifts.

Thus, *Dincharya* and *Ritucharya* can be seen as early frameworks of chronobiological regulation, offering strategies to stabilize internal rhythms and promote resilience through time-adapted living.

Dincharya and its modern correlation

Dincharya routine	Study	Evidence	Ayurvedic view	Correlation
Morning (Brahmamuhūrta – 4:30–6 AM)	(Czeisler et al., 1999) ^[67]	Cortisol peaks early morning, enhancing alertness, immunity, and bowel movement regularity.	(Caraka Samhita Sūtrasthāna 5): <i>Brahmamuhūrta utthāna</i> (waking before sunrise) promotes health, longevity, and clarity	Cortisol's early rise and synchronized gut motility explain why <i>Ayurveda</i> prescribes waking at <i>Brahmamuhūrta</i> for elimination, meditation, and <i>svasthya rakṣaṇa</i> .
Morning hygiene (Dantadhāvana, Anjana, Abhyanga, Snāna)	Nater et al (1) ^[68]	Morning oral care and bathing reduce stress hormone reactivity and improve circadian entrainment.	(Suśruta Samhita Cikitsāsthāna 24): Morning cleansing rituals (brushing, oil pulling, collyrium, massage, bath) purify channels and enhance sensory strength	Morning hygiene aligns with circadian regulation of hormones, oral microbiota, and stress resilience.
Ahāra (Meals and Digestion)	(Johnston et al., 2016) ^[69]	Evidence: Midday is optimal for digestion and glucose handling due to peak insulin sensitivity and gut activity	<i>Madhyāhna</i> (midday) is <i>Agni's peak</i> , so lunch should be the heaviest meal. (Caraka Samhita Sūtrasthāna 6)	Chrononutrition evidence supports the <i>Ayurvedic dictum</i> that the strongest digestive fire occurs at midday.
Evening (Sandhyākāla – Sunset)	Scheer FAJL, Hilton MF, (Mantzoros & Shea, 2009) ^[70]	Evidence: Eating late at night leads to impaired glucose tolerance, weight gain, and circadian disruption.	(Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya Sūtrasthāna 2): Light food in the evening; avoid late-night meals.	<i>Ayurveda's</i> warning against heavy food at night aligns with modern data on metabolic harm of evening eating.
Sleep (Ratri and Nidra)	(Walker, 2009) ^[71]	Evidence: Sleep regulates memory consolidation, emotional regulation, and immune function.	(Caraka Samhita Sūtrasthāna 21): <i>Nidrā</i> is one of the <i>Trayopastambha</i> (three pillars of life); proper night sleep sustains body, mind, and <i>Ojas</i> .	Correlation: Modern neuroscience confirms <i>Ayurveda's</i> emphasis on timely, restorative night sleep for health

Ritucharya and its modern correlation

Ritu	Modern study	Ayurvedic view	Correlation
1.) Vasanta (Spring) वसन्ते वसन्ति दोषाः शरीरस्थाः कफप्रभवाः। ...” (Caraka Samhita, Sūtrasthāna 6/22)	(Wucher et al., 2022) ^[72]	In Vasanta, <i>Kapha</i> accumulated during Hemanta liquefies due to rising temperature, leading to heaviness, lethargy, and diseases like <i>Kaphaja Jvara</i> if not managed.	Modern studies showing spring-specific gene expression shifts and metabolic activation reflect the <i>Ayurvedic</i> view that spring is a time of physiological transition, requiring <i>Ritucharya</i> (like <i>Vamana</i> , light food, exercise) to prevent <i>Kapha</i> disorders.

2.) Grīṣma (Summer) “ग्रीष्मे पित्तं च वृद्धयर्थं वायुश्च संप्रसंचितः।” (Aṣṭāṅga Hrdaya, Sūtrasthāna 3/17)	(Davenport et al., 2014) ^[73]	In Grīṣma, <i>Pitta</i> increases and <i>Vāta</i> accumulates due to heat and dryness; <i>Agni</i> remains strong, but body strength reduces; heavy physical exertion is discouraged.	Seasonal microbiome changes during hot months parallel the Ayurvedic observation that metabolism and gut ecology shift under heat stress, necessitating cooling, light, and hydrating diet.
3. Varṣā (Monsoon) “वर्षास्वग्निर्विपर्ययात् ... दोषा बहवो भवन्ति।” (Caraka Saṁhitā, Sūtrasthāna 6/27)	(Smits et al., 2017) ^[74]	In Varṣā, <i>Agni</i> weakens due to cloud cover, humidity, and vitiation of <i>Vāta</i> and <i>Pitta</i> . Digestion becomes unstable, predisposing to <i>Aam</i> formation and gastrointestinal disease.	Instability of gut microbiota and pathogen exposure in rainy season validates the Ayurvedic principle that Varṣā is the season of weakest digestion, requiring <i>Laghu</i> , <i>Snigdha</i> , and easily digestible food.
Śarad (Autumn / post-monsoon) “शरदि पित्तं प्रकुप्यति।” (Suśruta Saṁhitā, Sūtrasthāna 6/10)	(Guo et al., 2021) ^[75]	In Śarad, accumulated <i>Pitta</i> gets aggravated by the post-rain heat and clear skies, causing disorders like <i>Raktapitta</i> , <i>Pittaja Jvara</i> , and skin diseases.	Autumn-specific microbiome and metabolic shifts correspond with classical recognition of <i>Pitta</i> predominance, underscoring the need for cooling, bitter, and light dietary regimen.
Hemanta (Early Winter) “हेमन्ते बलवदग्निः ... गुरुस्निग्धान्नं जीर्यति।” (Caraka Saṁhitā, Sūtrasthāna 6/16)	(Koliada et al., 2020) ^[76]	In Hemanta, <i>Agni</i> is strongest, body strength is highest, and nourishment is easily digested; heavy, unctuous food is advised.	Winter enrichment of gut microbiota and increased metabolic stability reflect the strong digestive capacity (<i>Jātharāgni bala</i>) described in Ayurveda.
Śīśira (Late Winter) “शिशिरेऽपि हि तस्मिन्नेव मार्गेण ... कफवृद्धिः।” (Aṣṭāṅga Hrdaya, Sūtrasthāna 3/19)	(Lakshmikanth et al., 2020) ^[77]	In Śīśira, the extreme cold aggravates <i>Kapha</i> and <i>Vāta</i> while <i>Agni</i> remains strong internally; immunity is good, but external cold may predispose to respiratory disease.	Modern data showing strong immune activation and gut microbial shifts in peak winter align with Ayurveda’s description of <i>Agni bala</i> but increased <i>Kapha</i> dominance., <i>Kapha</i> increases, while <i>Agni</i> remains strong internally

REFERENCES

- Monier Williams M. A dictionary English and Sanskrit. Delhi.
- Rao Mangalagowri V. Text Book of Swasthavritta. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2007.
- Kaviraj Atridev Gupta Vidyalkar, Ashtanga Sangrah; Nirnaya Sagar press, Mumbai, 1951.
- Kaviraj Atridev Gupta Vidyalkar, Ashtanga Hridaya; Jay Krishnadas Haridas gupta Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi, 1950.
- Panda SK. Basic Principles of Kriya Sharir. New Delhi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2006.
- Brahmavarchas. Ayurved Darshan. Shantikunj: Vedmata Gayatri Trust, 2005.
- Pandey PD. Swasthya Rakshak. Indore: Nirogdham Prakashan, 2004.
- Sharma A. Watch Your Food. Ayurveda Health Tourism, 2009; 12: 17-21.
- Ashtanga Hridayam of Vagbhata. Pandit Hari Sadashiv Sastri Paradkar, Sutrasthana, Ch. 2, Verse 1. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2010; 23.
- Sushruta Samhita of Dalhan and Gayadas. Edited by Keval Krushna Thakral. Sutrasthana, Ch. 15, Verse 41. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientaliya, 2014; 179.
- Ashtanga Hridayam of Vagbhata. Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch. 1, Verse 14. Delhi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana, 2009; 11.
- Ashtanga Hridayam of Vagbhata. Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch. 12, Verses 34–44. Delhi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana, 2009; 197–198.
- Sushruta Samhita of Dalhan and Gayadas. Edited by Keval Krushna Thakral. Sutrasthana, Ch. 21, Verse 36. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientaliya, 2014; 260.
- Ashtanga Hridayam of Vagbhata. Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch. 2, Verse 1. Delhi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana, 2009; 27.
- Chaturvedi G, Pandey K, editor, (1st Ed.) Charak Samhita of Agnivesha Vol-1, Sutrasthanam, Matrashiteeya- adhyaya, Chapter 5. Varanasi Chaukhamba Vishvabharti Prakashana, Reprint, 2017; 113-133.
- Shastri AD, editor, (1st Ed.) Vol-1, Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Chikitsasthanam, anaagat-baadha-pratishedhaniya- adhyaya, Chapter 24, reprint, 2017; 133-143.
- Tripathi R, editor, (1st Ed.) Vol-1, Ashtangahridayam of Srimadvagbhata, Sutrasthanam, dinacharya-adhyayam, Chapter 2, reprint, 2012; 27: 42.
- Vagbhata, Astanga Samgraha, Hindi Commentry by Kaviraj Atridev Gupta, Sutrasthana Ch 1 verse 1 Chaukhamba Krushnadasa Academy, Varanasi, 2016; 19.
- Vagbhat, Astanga Samgraha, Hindi Commentry by Kaviraj Atridev Gupta, Sutrasthana Ch 1

- verse 1 Chaukhamba Krushnadasa Academy, Varanasi, 2016; 19.
20. The awakening cortisol response: methodological issues and significance. *Stress*. Clow A, Thorn L, Evans P, Hucklebridge F., 2004 Mar 1; 7(1): 29-37.
 21. Cortisol and immunity. *Medical hypotheses*. Jefferies WM., 1991 Mar 1; 34(3): 198-208.
 22. A Decent Science Behind the Brahma Muhurta Gupta R, Shukla O, Shrivastava V, P. IJAHM, 2017 Nov-Dec.; 7(6): 3005-9.
 23. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 7 verse 65, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 130.
 24. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 4 verse 12-13, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 58.
 25. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 1 verse 8, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 7-8.
 26. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 4 verse 2-7, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 57-58.
 27. Charak Samhita of Agnivesha, Ayurved Dipika Commentry edited by Yadavji Trikamji, Sutrasthan 5 verse 71 Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, 2008; 42.
 28. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 2, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 28.
 29. Ashtang hridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 2, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 28.
 30. Are all additives of toothpastes rational? Mani A, Thawani V; *Journal of Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences*, 2019 Jul 1; 24(2): 71.a.
 31. Charak Samhita of Agnivesha, Ayurved Dipika Commentry edited by Yadavji Trikamji, Sutrasthana 5 verse 74-75 Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, 2008; 42.
 32. Ohmori M, Baba R, Miyazaki A, Sato H, Katano S, Sawaki A, Tanabe S, Masatuki N, Yasukawa T, Hasegawa A, Imade S. P19 A study for the effect of tongue cleaning. *Oral Diseases*, 2005 Mar; 11: 111-2.
 33. Charak Samhita of Agnivesha, Ayurved Dipika Commentry edited by Yadavji Trikamji, Sutrasthan 5 verse 78-80 Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Varanasi, 2008; 42.
 34. Effect of Oil Pulling with Sesame Oil on Plaque-induced Gingivitis: A Microbiological Study. Saravanan, D, Ramkumar, S., & Vineetha, K. *Journal of Oro-facial Research*, 1970; 3(3): 175-180.
 35. Efficacy of oil pulling with sesame oil in comparison with other oils and chlorhexidine for oral health: a systematic review. Jeevan S, Sindhu R, Manipal S, Prabu D, Mohan R, Bharathwaj VV; *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2019 Nov 1; 11(11): 3573-8.
 36. Griessl T, Zechel-Gran S, Olejniczak S, Weigel M, Hain T, Domann E. High-resolution taxonomic examination of the oral microbiome after oil pulling with standardized sunflower seed oil and healthy participants: A pilot study. *Clinical Oral Investigations*, 2021 May; 25(5): 2689-703.
 37. Oil Pulling Revolution: The Natural Approach to Dental Care, Whole-Body Detoxification and Disease Prevention by. Michelle Coleman Publisher: Ulysses Press (28 April 2015), Language: English, ISBN-10: 1612434428, ISBN-13: 978-1612434421
 38. Ashtanghridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 4-5, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 28-29.
 39. Ashtanghridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 5, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 28-29.
 40. Wakde VS, Belge VA, Bhamkar VS. Prevention of Akalaja Jara through Swasthavritta Practices. In *Proceeding of International Conference Dirghayu-2021* 2021 Nov 18; 73.
 41. Susruta, Susruta Samhita, Ayurveda tatva sandipika Hindi Commentry by Kaviraj. Ambika dutt Shastri, Uttartantra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Samsthana, Varanasi, 2001; 77: 103.
 42. Ashtanghridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 20 verse 39, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 306.
 43. Ashtanghridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 20 verse 28-34, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi; 2009; 302-303.
 44. Nesari T, Kadam S, Vyas Met al. AYURAKSHA, a prophylactic Ayurvedic immunity boosting kit reducing positivity percentage of IgGCOVID-19 among frontline Indian Delhi police personnel: A non-randomized controlled intervention trial. *Front Public Health*. 2022 Aug 16; 10: 920126. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2022.920126. PMID: 36052011; PMCID: PM9424736.
 45. Patil, Rajkala & Patil, Panchakshari & Thakar, Anup B. Efficacy of Nasya (nasal medication) in coma: A case study. *Ancient Science of Life*, 2016; 35: 232. 10.4103/verse0257-7941.188188
 46. Ashtanghridayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 8-10, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 30-31.
 47. Ferber SG, Laudon M, Kuint J, Weller A, Zisapel N. Massage therapy by mothers enhances the adjustment of circadian rhythms to the nocturnal period in full-term infants. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*., 2002 Dec 1; 23(6): 410-5.
 48. A case report on the management of Akaala Jara with special reference to Premature Ageing

- Sreejaya.1*, ShaikhF.2, DiggaviM.3 (2022): MAY versus Case Report.
49. Koyama T, Kobayashi K, Hama T, Murakami K, Ogawa R. Standardized Scalp Massage Results in Increased Hair Thickness by Inducing Stretching Forces to Dermal Papilla Cells in the Subcutaneous Tissue. *Eplasty*. 2016 Jan 25; 16:e8. PMID: 26904154; PMCID: PMC4740347.
 50. The effect of a scalp massage on stress hormone, blood pressure, and heart rate of healthy female In-Hong Kim, PhD1), Tae-Young Kim, PhD2), Young-Wan Ko, PhD3)*2016.
 51. Fazeli MS, Pourrahmat MM, Liu M, Guan L, Collet JP. The Effect of Head Massage on the Regulation of the Cardiac Autonomic Nervous System: A Pilot Randomized Crossover Trial. *J Altern Complement Med*, 2016 Jan; 22(1): 75-80. doi: 10.1089/verseacm.2015.0141. Epub 2015 Nov 12. PMID: 26562003323
 52. Ferber SG, Laudon M, Kuint J, Weller A, Zisapel N. Massage therapy by mothers enhances the adjustment of circadian rhythms to the nocturnal period in full-term infants. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*, 2002 Dec 1; 23(6): 410-5.
 53. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 11-12, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 33.
 54. Jia RX, Liang JH, Xu Y, Wang YQ. Effects of physical activity and exercise on the cognitive function of patients with Alzheimer disease (AD): a meta-analysis. *BMC Geriatr.*, 2019 Jul 2; 19(1): 181. doi: 10.1186/verses12877-019-1175-2. PMID: 31266451; PMCID: PMC6604129.
 55. Börjesson M, Onerup A, Lundqvist S, Dahlöf B. Physical activity and exercise lower blood pressure in individuals with hypertension: narrative review of 27 RCTs. *Br J Sports Med*, 2016 Mar; 50(6): 356-61. doi: 10.1136/versebj sports-2015-095786. Epub 2016 Jan 19. PMID: 26787705.
 56. Umpierre D, Ribeiro PA, Kramer CK, Leitão CB, Zucatti AT, AzevedoMJ, Gross JL, Ribeiro JP, Schaan BD. Physical activity advice only or structured exercise training and association with HbA1c levels in type 2 diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA*, 2011 May 4; 305(17): 1790-9. doi: 10.1001/versejama.2011.576. PMID: 21540423.
 57. Hardcastle SJ, Taylor AH, Bailey MP, Harley RA, Hagger MS. Effectiveness of a motivational interviewing intervention on weight loss, physical activity and cardiovascular disease risk factors: a Randomised controlled trial with a 12-month post-intervention follow-up. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*, 2013 Mar 28; 10: 40. doi: 10.1186, verse 1479-5868-10-40. PMID: 23537492; PMCID: PMC3639183
 58. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 13-14, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 33-34.
 59. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2 verse 17-18, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 34-35.
 60. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 8 verse 1-3, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 135-141.
 61. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 5 verse 1-8, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 66-85.
 62. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 7verse 1-46, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 120-127.
 63. CharakSamhita of Agnivesha, Ayurved Dipika Commentry edited by Yadavji Trikamji, Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan, Vimanasthana 1 verse 21.-26 Varanasi, 2008; 235- 237.
 64. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2verse 9-48, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 34-41.
 65. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 12verse 59, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 160.
 66. Ashtanghridayayam of Vagbhata, Saroj Hindi Vyakhya, Sutrasthana, Ch 2verse 20-21, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Prakashana Delhi, 2009; 37.
 67. Czeisler CA, Duffy JF, Shanahan TL, et al. Stability, precision, and near-24-hour period of the human circadian pacemaker. *Science*, 1999; 284(5423): 2177-2181. doi:10.1126/science.284.5423.2177.
 68. Circadian rhythms and metabolism: from the brain to the periphery. *J Clin Invest.*, 2013; 123(3): 1-9. doi:10.1172/JCI67800.
 69. Johnston JD, Ordovás JM, Scheer FAJL, Turek FW. Circadian rhythms, metabolism, and chrononutrition in rodents and humans. *Adv Nutr.*, 2016; 7(2): 399-406. doi:10.3945/an.115.010777.
 70. Mantzoros CS, Shea SA. Adverse metabolic and cardiovascular consequences of circadian misalignment. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.*, 2009; 106(11): 4453-4458. doi:10.1073/pnas.0808180106.
 71. Walker MP. The role of sleep in cognition and emotion. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.*, 2009; 1156: 168-197. doi:10.1111/j.1749-6632.2009.04416.x
 72. Wucher V, Sodaei R, Amador R, Irimia M, Guigó R. Day-night and seasonal variation of human gene expression across tissues. *PLoS Biol.*, 2023; 21(2): e3001986. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.3001986.
 73. Davenport ER, Mizrahi-Man O, Michelini K, Barreiro LB, Ober C, Gilad Y. Seasonal variation in human gut microbiome composition. *PLoS ONE.*, 2014; 9(3): e90731. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0090731.

74. Smits SA, Leach J, Sonnenburg ED, et al. Seasonal cycling in the gut microbiome of the Hadza hunter-gatherers of Tanzania. *Science*, 2017; 357(6353): 802–806. doi:10.1126/science.aan4834.
75. Guo N, Zhang M, Zhang Y, et al. Seasonal dynamics of diet–gut microbiota interaction in wild golden snub-nosed monkeys. *Nat Commun.*, 2021; 12(1): 1–10. doi:10.1038/s41522-021-00207-6.
76. Koliada A, Moseiko V, Romanenko M, Piven L, Lushchak O, Kryzhanovska N, Guryanov V, Vaiserman A. Seasonal variation in gut microbiota composition: cross-sectional evidence from Ukrainian population. *BMC Microbiol.*, 2020; 20(1): 100. doi:10.1186/s12866-020-01786-8.
77. Lakshmikanth T, Srinivasan S, Raghavendra S, et al. Seasonal variation in gut microbiota composition: cross-sectional evidence from Indian population. *BMC Microbiol.*, 2020; 20(1): 100. doi:10.1186/s12866-020-01786-8.